

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Induction of sprouting resistance in Mahsuri

N. P. Sarma and Ashok Parnaik, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack - 753006, India

Mahsuri, a superior selection from an indica-japonica hybridization program, was selected in Malaysia and introduced into India in 1965. The high yielding, weakly photoperiod-sensitive tall variety (140-150 cm) is popular in the wet season because of its moderate resistance to lodging, medium-slender grains, and higher grain number per panicles. Mahsuri's major defect is its in situ germination of grains in the panicle (see figure). Natural precipitation and the humid climate as the crop matures in parts of India induce preharvest grain sprouting and cause heavy losses. Incorporation of moderate dormancy into Mahsuri would help reduce grain losses. Perhaps the best way of incorporating dormancy is to induce that trait through mutation. It is well known that genetic changes induced through mutations will be within the confines of the well-adapted genotype.

Mahsuri seeds were exposed to γ -rays (30 r), and also treated with the newly discovered and potent mutagen sodium azide (1.5×10^{-3} M for 6 hours; pH 3). A total of 8,540 M_2 plants derived from 362 M_1 plant families were raised to screen for induced mutations in 1979 kharif. Three panicles each of 3,150 M_2

Grains in panicles of Mahsuri often sprout before harvest (left). Sprouting resistance has been induced in M_2 lines of Mahsuri (right). CRRRI, India.

plants from γ -ray and azide treatments were subjected to germination tests immediately after harvest.

Presoaked panicles of Mahsuri parent, when rolled in paper towel and incubated at $32 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ normally sprout in 24-36 hours. But 71 M_2 lines were isolated in which sprouting was delayed considerably. The variants with delayed sprouting time have been advanced to the M_3 for critical and confirmatory sprouting tests to eliminate variations due to other than genetic causes. ■

Sri Lanka releases three new rice varieties

Rice Improvement Program, Department of Agriculture, Sri Lanka

The varietal release committee of the Department of Agriculture, Sri Lanka, has approved the release of three new improved rice varieties: BG400-1, BG276-5, and BW100.

BG400-1 (OB678/ / IR20/H4), bred at the Central Rice Breeding Station,

Batalagoda, is of medium growth duration (130 days). It has resistance to gall midge and to blast and bacterial blight diseases. Its grain is medium-long and stores better than BG90-2, the variety it is to replace.

BG276-5 (OB678/2*BG34-8), bred at Batalagoda, is an early-maturing variety (90 days) with resistance to gall midge and to blast and bacterial blight. Its grain is medium-long.

BW100 (H501//Podiwee A8/H5),

bred at the Agricultural Research Station, Bombuwela, is a 120-day samba rice variety recommended for cultivation

in the low-country wet zone of Sri Lanka. It is resistant to blast, has tolerance for iron toxicity and is

moderately resistant to gall midge and storage pests. It has good grain quality. ■

Performance of IET7041 in nitrogen variety trial

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A field trial was conducted on a black clayey soil with high organic matter content, medium phosphorus and high potassium contents, and a pH of 7.5 during kharif (Jun-Nov) 1979 at the Regional Center, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Maruteru, A. P. Six prerelease lines and two released varieties (Table 1) constituted the main plots, and four nitrogen levels were the subplots in a split-plot design with three replications. A basal applica-

Table 1. Details of entries in nitrogen variety trial, APAU, 1979 kharif.

IET no.	Designation	Cross	Maturity (days)	100-grain wt (g)	Rice type ^a
5656	RP975-109-2	Sona/RPW6-13	155	26	LB
5854	RP1017-76-1-4-3	Sona/Mahsuri	150	18	MS
6056	RP894-61-1-3-7-2	CR44-35/W12708	155	19	MS
6212	RP1064-14-2-2	RP31-49-2/Patnai 23	155	25	SB
6314	RP1045-23-2-1	RP31-49-2/LMN	160	25	SB
7041	MTU7029	Vasista/Mahsuri	155	19	MS
	Pankaj (check)		155	28	LB
	Mahsuri (check)		150	16	MS

^aLB = long, bold; SB = short, bold; MS = medium, slender.

tion of 30 kg P₂O₅ and 30 kg K₂O/ha was applied. Nitrogen was applied 50% at transplanting, 25% at 25 days after transplanting (DT), and 25% at 50 DT.

IET7041 (MTU7029), developed at APAU, yielded highest (Table 2). The optimum level of nitrogen for it was 30

kg/ha. It had the highest panicle number at all nitrogen levels.

IET7041 should be suited for good yields on soils with high organic matter at lower nitrogen inputs in kharif on the Krishna and Godavari deltas of A.P. ■

Table 2. Summary of results of nitrogen variety trial, APAU, 1979 kharif.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	IET7041	IET5656	Pankaj	IET6314	IET6056	IET6212	IET5854	Mahsuri (check)
0	5.9	5.1	5.0	4.6	5.0	4.1	4.5	3.8
30	6.0	5.2	4.9	4.8	4.3	4.1	4.1	3.2
60	6.3	5.2	5.0	4.8	4.1	4.4	3.7	3.2
90	6.4	4.8	4.6	4.3	4.5	4.3	3.0	2.4

C.D. (P = 0.05) for varieties, 0.6 t/ha; for nitrogen levels, 0.3 t/ha.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Studies on false-smut disease caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* on paddy in Karnataka, India

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False smut on paddy has occurred in Karnataka for more than 3 decades. The preliminary survey conducted for more than 5 years indicates that the disease occurs on both modern and local improved varieties throughout the state

during the kharif, particularly on varieties that are late sown and flower late (usually from November). The data collected indicate that the disease incidence on some varieties varies from less than 1% to more than 50%. The percentage of incidence has been taken on the panicle basis, irrespective of the number of smut balls formed on each panicle.

Some varieties showed less than 10% incidence: IET2885 (7.92), IET2886 (5.62), IET1789 (1.08), IR26 (0.48), IET2295 (4.33), Sona (0.77), and IET3359 (1.42). Varieties among the IRON entries of kharif 1976 that showed

more than 50% disease incidence were IR4427-315-2-3, IR4442-45-2-1, IR4722-36-1, IR5853-31, and IR2863-31-3. Among the NSN entries of kharif 1976 with more than 50% disease incidence were RP894-61-1-10-7, RP974-4-7-6-2, RP6-590-22-5-4-1, Biplat, and IR2071-588-1-1-1.

Further information indicates that the number of smut balls varies from 1 to 6/panicle; 2-4 smut balls have been observed on more than 50% of infected panicles; 1-6 smut balls have been observed on 16%, 32%, 26%, 14%, 8.20%, and 3.80% of infected panicles.